

STRATEGIC ALLOCATION OF STATCOM FOR POWER LOSS MINIMIZATION AND VOLTAGE STABILITY IMPROVEMENT IN POWER GRID USING FIREFLY ALGORITHM

A. Jimoh¹, M. T. Adebayo¹, F. K. Ariyo¹ and S. O. Ayanlade^{*2}

¹ Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

² Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Lead City University, Ibadan.

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*samson.ayanlade@lcu.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on reducing power losses in power systems and enhancing stability and loadability by using the Newton Raphson power flow approach to determine strategic locations for installing the Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) controllers. Identifying suitable locations for these costly FACTS controllers, such as the static synchronous compensator (STATCOM), is critical and requires satisfying several criteria. STATCOM can be installed on buses and transmission lines to achieve this goal. This paper utilized the Firefly Algorithm (FA) to strategically allocate a STATCOM unit to minimize power losses. The methodology is tested on the IEEE 57-bus grid, comparing scenarios with and without STATCOM installations. The results identified bus 8 as the most effective location for the STATCOM, where significant voltage instability was observed. The optimal size of 200 MVar was selected to provide sufficient reactive power to stabilize voltage and improve power flow efficiency, addressing network congestion. The voltage stability of the network showed improvement, with the minimum voltage magnitude rising from 0.9185 in the base case to 0.95 per unit. Furthermore, the minimizations of real and reactive power losses were substantial, amounting to 34.59% and 33.23%, respectively. These findings highlight how effectively the FA optimizes STATCOM placement, leading to improved performance of the power grid.

Keywords: Power loss minimization, Voltage stability improvement, STATCOM, Firefly algorithm, Strategic location, Power grid

INTRODUCTION

The continuous increase in electricity demand has significantly stressed power systems, leading to operations near or even above their capacity limits. This strain reduces the loadability of the power system—defined as the maximum power that can be transferred through transmission lines before voltage instability occurs—which can result in suboptimal performance and increase the risk of system instability (Liu, 2019). One critical issue is voltage breakdown, where the bus voltage magnitude drops precipitously to dangerously low levels, potentially causing widespread blackouts (Adegoke and Sun, 2023). Ensuring that the power system can reliably meet load demand is thus of paramount importance.

A primary cause of voltage breakdown is insufficient reactive power within the system, often stemming from overloading (Haes Alhelou *et al.*, 2019). To address this challenge, it is essential to implement measures that can inject reactive power into the network effectively. Various methods have been researched and developed to hit this target, with one of the most promising being the deployment of Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) controllers (Aduragba, 2017; Mahmood *et al.*, 2017; Shinde *et al.*, 2016).

Among FACTS devices, the Static Synchronous

Compensator (STATCOM) stands out as a particularly effective solution. STATCOMs provide dynamic reactive power support, enhancing voltage stability and minimizing power losses (Mumtahina *et al.*, 2023; Siddiqui and Rani, 2015). Unlike the traditional approach of expanding generation capacity to meet increased demand—which is prohibitively expensive—FACTS devices offer a cost-effective alternative (Asawa and Al-Attiyah, 2016; Chatzivasileiadis *et al.*, 2011). They boost the effectiveness and reliability of the grid without the need for significant infrastructural investments (Ayanlade *et al.*, 2021).

This paper focuses on the strategic allocation of the STATCOM in the power grid to optimize power loss reduction and voltage stability. By leveraging the Firefly Algorithm (FA), an advanced optimization technique inspired inherent characteristics of fireflies, our goal is to identify the optimal location and size for STATCOMs. The FA's robustness and efficiency make it well-suited for solving complex optimization problems in power systems (Nayak *et al.*, 2020; Senjyu *et al.*, 2021).

This research is important because it has the potential to improve both the operational effectiveness and dependability of grids. By strategically deploying STATCOMs, we can ensure a more stable and resilient power grid, capable of meeting growing electricity demands without compromising performance. This study advances

the field of power system optimization and offers practical guidance for utilities aiming to implement cost-effective solutions for managing reactive power and enhancing voltage stability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have focused on optimizing the strategic allocation of STATCOMs in power grids. This section reviews key works in this area, presenting a brief survey of various methods and solutions.

Okelola *et al.* (2021) utilized Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) for STATCOM strategic allocation in transmission grid. In their study, the authors applied PSO implemented in the MATLAB environment to optimize STATCOM deployment in the modified IEEE 14-node system. Their results showed a 6.90% minimization in total real power loss and improved voltage levels at nodes 7 and 13, which had previously exceeded the upper voltage limits. These adjustments brought the voltages within acceptable ranges and enhanced the overall system voltage profile, highlighting the significant potential of optimal STATCOM allocation to improve both the efficiency and operational stability of power networks.

Samal and Roshan (2020) introduced the Sailfish Optimizer Algorithm (SFOA) to optimize STATCOM location and capacity in the IEEE 14-bus power grid. Their study aimed to stabilize voltage magnitudes and diminish overall real power losses under four different loading conditions. The authors employed Newton Raphson’s approach to carry out power flow analysis and calculate voltage magnitudes and power losses. They also conducted a comparative analysis between SFOA and the Moth-Flame Optimization Algorithm (MFOA), demonstrating that SFOA outperformed MFOA in achieving significant improvements in voltage magnitudes and TRPL by optimally placing and sizing the STATCOM.

Singh and Tiwari (2018) tackled the challenge of power systems operating under stressed conditions caused by economic constraints, right-of-way limitations, and regulatory factors. They emphasized the utilization of FACTS devices, particularly the STATCOM, for flexible control through the injection or absorption of reactive power. Taking cost factors into account, their research aimed to identify the optimal quantity, placement, and sizing of Holomorphic Embedded Load-Flow (HELFL) model of the STATCOM within power systems. They employed Improved Sine Cosine Optimization Algorithm (ISCA) for this purpose. The IEEE 30-node grid was considered as the test network for the algorithm, and the results were compared with those obtained using the SCA and Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO), demonstrating the efficacy of ISCA in the strategic placement and sizing of the HELFL model.

Taher *et al.* (2018) used the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) to find the optimal location of STATCOMs in transmission grid. They achieved the highest system loadability using Continuation Power Flow

(CPF) and integrated WOA with CPF to optimize a multi-objective function focused on increasing loadability while minimizing both the voltage stability index and losses. To verify the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, the standard IEEE 57-bus network was employed. The outcomes were compared with those of MFO technique. The results highlighted the proposed algorithm’s capability to address the optimization problem effectively, providing competitive solutions. The comparison revealed that the approach is both efficient and robust, significantly improving power system voltage stability and loadability while reducing total power losses, and achieving quicker and more stable convergence.

STRUCTURE AND OPERATION OF THE STATCOM CONTROLLER

A standard STATCOM setup includes multi-level Voltage Source Converters (VSCs) utilizing Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs), phase reactors, and a step-up transformer. It is connected to the grid in a shunt configuration and produces a regulated internal voltage waveform to either supply or absorb reactive current. The STATCOM fundamental structure is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Basic STATCOM Configuration (Saboori et al., 2015)

The VSC is a key electronic component that transforms DC voltage into AC output voltage magnitudes with defined frequency, amplitude, and phase characteristics. The reactive power exchange between the network and the converter is regulated by varying the amplitude of the converter’s three-phase output voltage V_{vsc} . When V_{vsc} exceeds the AC bus voltage V_{ac} (i.e., $V_{vsc} > V_{ac}$), the STATCOM injects reactive power into the system. Conversely, if V_{vsc} is lower than V_{ac} (i.e., $V_{vsc} < V_{ac}$), the STATCOM absorbs reactive power from the network. If V_{vsc} & V_{ac} are equal (i.e., $V_{vsc} = V_{ac}$), the STATCOM remains in standby mode. The power flow governing the STATCOM’s operation are detailed in Equations (1) to (4).

$$P_m = P_{sh} + \sum_{j=1}^N |V_m| |V_j| |Y_{mj}| \cos(\theta_{mj} - \delta_{mj}) \quad (1)$$

$$Q_m = Q_{sh} + \sum_{j=1}^N |V_m| |V_j| |Y_{mj}| \sin(\theta_{mj} - \delta_{mj}) \quad (2)$$

$$P_{sh} = G_{sh} |V_m|^2 - |V_m| |V_{sh}| |Y_{sh}| \cos(\theta_{msh} - \delta_{sh}) \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{sh} = B_{sh} |V_m|^2 - |V_m| |V_{sh}| |Y_{sh}| \sin(\theta_{msh} - \delta_{sh}) \quad (4)$$

In this context, V_m represents the voltage magnitude at bus m , and V_{sb} is the shunt voltage injected. The active and reactive powers at bus m are denoted as P_m and Q_m , respectively, while P_{sb} & Q_{sb} indicate the active & reactive powers associated with the STATCOM bus. The conductance, susceptance, and admittance of the STATCOM are denoted by G_{sb} , B_{sb} and Y_{sb} , respectively. Additionally, Y_{mj} represents the branch admittance between nodes m & j , and N stands for the total number of buses.

STRATEGIC ALLOCATION OF STATCOM

The strategic location and capacity of STATCOM unit was optimized using the FA, with the Newton Raphson technique employed to assess the system's voltage profiles and power losses. This section is subdivided into two subsections: first, defining an appropriate objective function to evaluate the performance of each firefly; and second, specifying the firefly's position vector and characterizing infeasible solutions based on the objective function.

Power Flow Analysis

This study addresses the resolution of a system of nonlinear algebraic equations representing the power system's steady-state conditions. The Newton Raphson technique was employed to solve these power flow equations. Additionally, the power equations specific to the STATCOM were incorporated into the established load flow algorithm.

Objective Function

This study's main goal is to strategically position and size a STATCOM within a power grid to diminish total active power loss and maintain voltage stability throughout the network. The STATCOM's location and capacity are optimized utilizing the FA, which is inspired by the behavior of fireflies.

The overall power loss in the grid is the aggregate of power losses across all branches. Mathematically, the objective function to optimize this loss, is represented by Equation (5).

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^N P_{loss,i} \quad (5)$$

Where, P_{loss} = total active power loss, $P_{loss,i}$ = active power loss in the i th branch. Active power loss in each branch i can be calculated by Equation (6)

$$P_{loss,i} = R_i \left(\frac{|V_i|^2 + |V_j|^2 - 2|V_i||V_j| \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j)}{Z_i^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where, R_i = resistance of the i th branch, $|V_i|$ & $|V_j|$ = voltage magnitudes at the sending and receiving ends of the i th branch. θ_i & θ_j = voltage angles at the sending and receiving ends of the i th branch, respectively, Z_i = impedance of the i th branch. The FA optimizes the placement and sizing of the STATCOM by iteratively adjusting its position and capacity to achieve the minimum possible value of P_{loss} .

Constraints

The optimization problem must satisfy the constraints as follow.

i. *Voltage Limits:*

$$V_{min} \leq |V_i| \leq V_{max} \quad (7)$$

where, V_{min} and V_{max} = minimum and maximum allowable voltage magnitudes, respectively, and $|V_i|$ = voltage value at i th bus.

ii. *Power Flow Balance:*

$$P_{G_i} - P_{D_i} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |V_j| (G_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j)) \quad (8)$$

$$Q_{G_i} - Q_{D_i} = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |V_j| (G_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j) - B_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j)) \quad (9)$$

where, P_{G_i} & Q_{G_i} = active & reactive power generations at bus i , P_{D_i} & Q_{D_i} = active & reactive demands at i th bus, and G_{ij} & B_{ij} = conductance & susceptance of the branch between buses i & j .

iii. *STATCOM Capacity Limits:*

$$Q_{STATCOM,min} \leq Q_{STATCOM} \leq Q_{STATCOM,max} \quad (10)$$

Where, $Q_{STATCOM,min}$ & $Q_{STATCOM,max}$ = minimum and maximum reactive power compensation capabilities of the STATCOM, respectively, and $Q_{STATCOM}$ is the reactive power provided by the STATCOM.

Thermal Limits of Transmission Lines:

$$S_{ij} \leq S_{ij,max} \quad (11)$$

Where, S_{ij} = apparent power flow in the branch between buses i & j , and $S_{ij,max}$ = maximum allowable apparent power flow for that branch.

The FA considers these constraints while optimizing the location and capacity of the STATCOM to ensure a feasible and effective solution for loss reduction and voltage instability mitigation.

Firefly Algorithm

The FA is a metaheuristic optimization method inspired by the bioluminescence of fireflies. Known for its simplicity

and effectiveness in tackling complex optimization problems, the algorithm mimics the flashing patterns of fireflies to discover optimal solutions. The key concepts of FA are as follows:

i. Attractiveness and Movement:

Each firefly's attractiveness is directly related to its brightness, which is evaluated based on the objective function. Fireflies move towards brighter (more attractive) fireflies. The movement of a firefly towards another is described by the Equation (12):

$$\vec{x}_i(t+1) = \vec{x}_i(t) + \beta_0 \exp(-\gamma r^2) (\vec{x}_j(t)) + \alpha \text{rand} \quad (12)$$

Where, $\vec{x}_i(t+1)$ = location of firefly i at the next iteration, $\vec{x}_i(t)$ = present location of firefly i , $\vec{x}_j(t)$ = location of a brighter firefly j , β_0 = attractiveness at the distance $r = 0$, γ = light absorption coefficient, α is the randomization parameter, rand = random no. between 0 & 1, r = distance between fireflies i & j , computed as $r = \|\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j\|$.

ii. Attractiveness Decrease:

A firefly's attractiveness diminishes as its distance from other fireflies' increases, modeled by the exponential term in the movement equation in the Equation (12).

iii. Randomization:

A random factor is introduced, represented by the term, to prevent premature convergence and effectively explore the search space. The FA iterates through these steps, updating the positions of fireflies based on their attractiveness and distance, to identify the best solution to the problem.

Implementation of FA for Strategic Placement and Sizing of STATCOM

Step 1: Initialization: Enter the parameters of the FA. Each firefly's position vector consists of Bus index (1 to 57) and STATCOM size (e.g., in MVar).

Step 2: Objective Function: It is defined as the overall power loss of the network as per Equation (5).

Step 3: The Newton-Raphson method is employed to solve the power flow problem of the IEEE 57-bus system, with the STATCOM placed at the bus identified by the Firefly Algorithm. This iterative method computes the voltage

magnitudes, angles, and power flows at all buses. By solving the power flow, the impact of the STATCOM on voltage stability and reactive power compensation can be evaluated. Additionally, the total power losses in the transmission lines are calculated, so as to assess the effectiveness of STATCOM in reducing active power losses and enhancing the overall efficiency of the power grid.

Step 4: Firefly Movement: Compute the attractiveness of each firefly based on their total power loss. Lower losses correspond to higher attractiveness. Also, update the position of each firefly as per Equation (12).

Step 5: Termination Criteria: Monitor changes in the objective function and stop if changes are minimal or a predefined number of iterations is reached.

Step 6: Post-Processing: Identify the firefly with the lowest total power loss as the optimal solution for the STATCOM placement and sizing.

A mapping of your network parameters with the FA's parameters is shown in Table 1

Description of IEEE 57-Bus Network

The IEEE 57-bus system was chosen because it serves as a standard benchmark in power system research. Its moderate size and complexity, with multiple generators and loads, make it ideal for testing optimization algorithms. This

Table 1: Mapping of FA Parameters with Network Parameters for Strategic STATCOM Allocation

FA Parameters	Network Parameters	Mapping Description
Objective Function	Active power loss	FA minimizes power loss while maintaining voltage stability.
Search Space Definition	Candidate buses for STATCOM placement, capacity limits	Defines feasible STATCOM locations and sizing options.
Light Intensity (Fitness Function)	Power loss reduction	Each firefly's brightness represents solution quality based on loss reduction.
Firefly Movement (Attraction and Randomness)	Network topology, voltage sensitivity, operational constraints	Fireflies move toward better solutions by exploring buses with greater voltage sensitivity.

system reflects practical challenges, making it suitable for validating the strategic allocation of STATCOM for power loss minimization and voltage stability improvement using the Firefly Algorithm. It comprises 57 buses, 80 branches, 7 generators, and 17 loads. The total real and reactive load of the network are 1250.8 MW and 336.4 MVar, respectively. This network serves as a standard benchmark for evaluating optimization techniques and power system analysis -methods. Figure 2 illustrates the one-line diagram of the network. The data for the buses and lines in this network was obtained from (Anand and Balaji, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation parameters used in the FA are presented in Table 2. These parameters were carefully selected based on a combination of literature recommendations, experimentation, and problem-specific requirements. The maximum iteration number and population size were chosen to balance computational time with solution quality. The light absorption coefficient, attractiveness, and

randomization parameters were configured to ensure the exploration-exploitation trade-off, crucial for avoiding local minima while converging toward an optimal solution. Additionally, the placement and sizing of the STATCOM demand precise parameter tuning to enhance harmonic minimization and power flow stability, which guided the final selections.

Figure 2: IEEE 57-Bus Single-Line Diagram (Moses and Kannan, 2022)

Table 2: FA Simulation Parameters

Parameters	Value
Number of fireflies (n):	100
Maximum iterations (T_{max}):	30
Initial attractiveness coefficient (β_0):	0.5
Absorption coefficient (γ):	1.0

Strategically Placement and Capacity of STATCOM

The application of the FA yielded the optimal size and placement of the STATCOM within the IEEE 57-bus network. The algorithm identified bus 8 as the optimal

location for the STATCOM, with a required capacity of 200 MVAR. This strategic placement is crucial for achieving the objective of diminishing overall active power loss and improving voltage stability. The convergence characteristics of the FA, demonstrating its effectiveness in finding the optimal solution, are shown in Figure 3. From Figure 3, it is noted that convergence was achieved after 4 iterations, indicating the rapid convergence of FA in solving complex optimization problems, especially in power grids.

Effect on Voltage Stability

The STATCOM impact on the voltage stability of the network was assessed through a comparison of the voltage profiles without and with the STATCOM integration as illustrated in Figure 4. Without the STATCOM, several buses experienced voltage levels outside the acceptable range, indicating instability and potential reliability issues in the power grid. Specifically, buses 25, 30, 31, 32, 33 and 34 exhibited voltage drops below the acceptable minimum of 0.95 p.u. After installing the STATCOM at the identified optimal location, the voltage profile across the network showed significant improvement. The voltage levels at critical buses such as 25, 30, 31, 32, 33 and 34 were restored to 0.95 p.u., which represents the minimum acceptable voltage limit, indicating enhanced voltage stability and reliability of the power grid.

Effect on Power Loss

The effectiveness of the STATCOM in reducing power losses was evaluated by comparing the real and reactive power losses before and after its placement.

i. Real Power Loss

The overall real power loss in the network without the STATCOM was 112.32 MW. With the STATCOM, the total real power loss was diminished to 73.466 MW, representing a reduction of 38.854 MW or 34.59%. The comparison of real power losses is illustrated in Figure 5.

ii. Reactive Power Loss

Similarly, the aggregate reactive loss without the STATCOM was 442.79 MVAR, and with the

Figure 3: Convergence Curve for FA

Figure 4: Voltage Profile Pre-and Post STATCOM

Figure 5: Active Power Loss Pre-and Post-STATCOM

Figure 6: Reactive Power Loss Pre-and Post-STATCOM

STATCOM, it decreased to 295.66 MVar, amounting to a reduction of 147.13 MVar or 33.23%. The comparison of reactive power losses is illustrated in Figure 6.

The results demonstrate that the FA is an effective optimization tool for the strategic allocation of STATCOM in power grids. The algorithm successfully identified the strategic location and capacity of the

STATCOM, leading to significant minimization in both real and reactive losses and substantial improvements in the voltage stability of the network.

The reduction in power losses contributes to increased overall efficiency of the power grid, leading to lower operational costs and enhanced reliability. The improved voltage profile ensures that the power system operates

within safe and stable voltage limits, reducing the risk of voltage instability and potential blackouts.

CONCLUSION

This study has utilized the FA to strategically allocate a STATCOM in the IEEE 57-bus network with the aim of improving voltage stability and minimizing active and reactive power losses to elevate the efficiency of the network. The results demonstrated that the FA effectively identified the strategic location and capacity of the STATCOM, leading to significant improvements in the network's performance.

The implementation of the STATCOM resulted in a notable enhancement of the voltage profile, bringing voltage levels within acceptable ranges, thereby ensuring the stability and reliability of the grid. Additionally, the overall active and reactive power losses were significantly reduced, contributing to increased overall efficiency and reduced operational costs.

The rapid convergence of FA, as evidenced by the convergence characteristics observed, underscores the algorithm's capability to handle complex optimization problems in power systems.

Future research could explore the application of FA to other aspects of power systems, such as the integration of Distributed Generation (DG) and Energy Storage Systems (ESS), to further enhance grid stability and efficiency. Moreover, the potential integration of the advanced machine learning techniques with FA could improve its adaptability and performance in dynamic and complex power system environments.

In summary, the strategic allocation of STATCOM using the FA presents a promising approach for enhancing the operational efficiency and stability of power grids, thus aiding in the creation of more reliable and resilient power systems.

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